

Synthesis of Dipentene and β -Terpinene

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Dipentene and β -terpinene have been synthesised by an application of the Wittig reaction with methyl-triphenylphosphonium iodide on 4-acetyl-1-methylcyclohex-1-ene and 4-isopropylcyclohex-3-enone respectively.

Dipentene, a monocyclic monoterpene hydrocarbon, is widely distributed in nature both in the *dextro* and *laevo* forms¹. On the basis of analytical and chemical studies² and synthetic evidence³, the constitution (I) has been assigned to the hydrocarbon.

The present investigations record a clean synthesis of dipentene, which is free from the ambiguity involved in the dehydration sequence in the earlier synthesis³.

4-Acetyl-1-methylcyclohex-1-ene (II), obtained from methyl vinyl ketone and isoprene in presence of a little of hydroquinone, was treated with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide in presence of sodium methoxide⁴ in methanol (acetone-free) to obtain dipentene (I) in 44% yield.

The compound (I) was characterised through its I R absorption spectrum, showing characteristic peaks⁵ for the synthetic sample at 886, 1634, and 3078 cm^{-1} .

β -Terpinene, another monocyclic monoterpene hydrocarbon, which does not occur in nature, has been assigned structure (III) on the basis of physical and chemical studies⁶.

1. Simonsen, 'The Terpenes', Vol. I, The University Press, Cambridge, 1947, p. 143.

2. *Idem, ibid.*, pp. 148, 149, 153.

3. Pinder, 'The Chemistry of the Terpenes', Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1960, pp. 50, 51.

4. Wittig and Schollkopf, *Ber.*, 1954, **87**, 1318.

5. Pinder, 'The Chemistry of the Terpenes', Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1960, p. 13; Cross, 'Introduction to Practical I.R. Spectroscopy', Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1960, p. 48.

6. Simonsen, 'The Terpenes', Vol. I, The University Press, Cambridge, 1947, pp. 186, 187, 188.

The present scheme records an unambiguous synthesis of β -terpinene along the following lines:

4-Isopropylcyclohex-3-en-1-one (V)⁷, obtained from 4-isopropylanisole (IV) via the modified Birch metal ammonia reduction⁸, was purified through sodium hydrogen sulphite addition compound. The ketone (V) was then submitted to the Wittig reaction⁹ with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide to furnish β -terpinene (III) in 50% yield.

The synthetic hydrocarbon (III) was characterised through its IR absorption spectrum, which showed peaks⁹ at 1375, 890, and 816 cm^{-1} .

• EXPERIMENTAL

4-Acetyl-1-methylcyclohex-1-ene (II).—The pure sample of this compound was obtained exactly according to the conditions mentioned before.

4-Isopropenyl-1-methylcyclohex-1-ene (I).—To a solution of methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (27.8 g.) and the preceding compound (II) (6 g.) in methanol (50 ml) was added, with constant stirring and under nitrogen atmosphere, sodium methoxide (prepared from 1.5 g. of Na) in methanol (40 ml). The addition was made at 55° and over a period of 10 minutes. The reaction mixture was stirred at 60° for another 8 hours during which the colour of the contents changed from yellow to red. The methanol was evaporated under vacuum and the residue extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°). The solution was washed with water and dried over sodium sulphate

The solvent was removed and the remaining oil after purification through alumina column was vacuum-distilled to afford a colorless oil, b.p. 61°/13-14 mm, yield 2.53 g. (44%), n_D^{17} 1.4725 (lit.¹⁰ reports n_D^{17} 1.473). (Found: C, 88.45; H, 11.44. Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$: C, 88.16; 11.84%).

IR absorption spectrum in CCl_4 showed characteristic peaks⁹ for the synthetic hydrocarbon (I) at 886, 1634, and 3078 cm^{-1} .

* Analysis by Drs. Woiler and Strauss, Oxford.

7. Birch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 593.

8. Wilds and Nelson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5360.

9. Mitzner and Theimer, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 3350.

10. Richter and Wolf, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 1720, 1724.

4-Isopropylcyclohex-3-enone (V) was prepared from *p*-isopropylanisole exactly according to the conditions mentioned earlier^{7,8}.

4-Isopropyl-1-methylenecyclohex-3-ene (III).—To a solution of methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (27.8 g.) and the preceding ketone (V) (4 g.) in methanol (acetone-free, 34 ml) was added, with constant stirring and under nitrogen atmosphere, sodium methoxide (prepared from 1.06 g. of Na) in methanol (27 ml). The addition was made at 55° and over a period of 10 minutes. The contents were stirred at 60° for another 8 hours during which the colour changed from yellow to red. The reaction mixture was then worked up as in (I) to provide a colorless oil, b.p. 60°/9-10mm, yield 2 g. (50%), n_D^{17} 1.4745 (lit.¹⁰ reports n_D^{17} 1.4754). (Found: C, 88.36; H, 11.63. Calc. for C₁₀H₁₆: C, 88.16; H, 11.84%).

The synthetic hydrocarbon (III) was characterised through I R absorption spectrum, which gave characteristic peaks⁹ at 1375, 890, and 816^{cm}⁻¹.

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